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Location-Based Power Control Mechanism for D2D Communication Underlying a Cellular System

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Outline

- ▶ D2D communication in cellular system
- ▶ Location-based power control mechanism
- ▶ Simulation environment
- ▶ Results
- ▶ Conclusions

D2D communication in cellular system

- ▶ Challenges
 - ▶ Mode selection
 - ▶ New **interference** patterns
 - ▶ Resource management
- ▶ Solutions
 - ▶ Resource management
 - ▶ **Power control**
 - ▶ Interference cancellation

Location-based power control mechanism

LTSIPC

- ▶ Assumptions
 - ▶ **Protect D2D receiver**
 - ▶ **Centralized** approach e.g. base station, specialized entity
 - ▶ Utilizes information about users **locations** to estimate the interference experienced by the D2D receiver
 - ▶ **estimate** the **distance** between devices and, consequently, the **interference** caused to the D2D receiver
 - ▶ it requires **no knowledge** of **channel coefficients**

Location-based power control mechanism

LTSIPC (Location-based Target SIR Power Control)

- ▶ SIR at D2D receiver

$$\xi_D = \frac{|h_{D2D}|^2 P_D d_{D2D}^{-\alpha}}{\sum_{i=1}^N |h_{DC_i}|^2 P_{C_i} d_{DC_i}^{-\alpha}}$$

- ▶ ξ_0 - SIR target

$$P_{DTX} = \frac{\xi_0 \sum_{i=1}^N |h_{DC_i}|^2 P_{C_i} d_{DC_i}^{-\alpha}}{|h_{D2D}|^2 d_{D2D}^{-\alpha}}$$

$$P_D = \min \left(P_{max}, \xi_0 d_{D2D}^{\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^N P_{C_i} d_{DC_i}^{-\alpha} \right)$$

Simulation environment

- ▶ Simulation tool (MACHINE) based on METIS guidelines
 - ▶ Deployment,
 - ▶ Channel Models,
 - ▶ Mobility
- ▶ OFDMA based system
- ▶ Macro base station operating in FDD
 - ▶ 3 sectors - same frequency band

Simulation environment

- ▶ 400 user - uniformly placed outside the buildings
 - ▶ 120 CUEs on pavements
 - ▶ 200 CUEs in cars
 - ▶ 40 D2D pairs (80 DUEs)
 - ▶ 15 of D2D pairs - pedestrian users,
 - ▶ 25 D2D pairs in cars
- ▶ D2D distance 0 to 100 m
- ▶ The resource allocation
 - ▶ Round-robin mechanism for CUEs
 - ▶ Random for D2D users
- ▶ OLPC mechanism for CUEs
- ▶ LTSIPC mechanism with SIR target of 20dB

Results

Transmit Power

All UEs

D2D users

Results

Spectral efficiency

System

D2D comm.

Conclusions

- ▶ Introduction of D2D communication
 - ▶ Decreased transmit power levels
 - ▶ Increased spectral efficiency and energy efficiency
- ▶ LTSIPC approach compared to OLPC approach:
 - ▶ higher transmit power outputs but better granularity of transmit power settings,
 - ▶ lower transmit power for D2D devices that are very close to each other,
 - ▶ better spectral efficiency
- ▶ Location-based approach doesn't require additional reports and measurements of the channel

